

Mitigating Software Integrity Attacks with Trusted computing

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KEYWORDS

Software Integrity Attacks,
Trusted Computing,
Time Distribution Network (TDN),
Trusted Platform Module(TPM),
Secure Boot,
End-To-End Security

ABSTRACT

Time Distribution Networks (TDNs) evolve as new technologies occur to ensure more accurate, reliable, and secure timing information. These networks typically exploit several distributed time servers, organized in a master-slave architecture, that communicate via dedicated timing protocols. From the security perspective, timing data must be protected since its modification or filtering can lead to grave consequences in different time-based contexts, such as health, energy, finance, or transportation. Thus, adequate countermeasures must be employed in all the stages and systems handling timing data from its calculation until it reach the final users. We consider a TDN offering highly accurate (nanosecond level) time synchronization through specific time unit devices that exploit terrestrial atomic or rubidium clocks and Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS) receivers. Such devices are appealing targets for attackers, who might exploit various attack vectors to compromise their functionality. We individuate three possible software integrity attacks against time devices, and we propose a solution to counter them by exploiting the cryptographic Trusted Platform Module (TPM), defined and supported by the Trusted Computing Group. We used remote attestation software for cloud environments, namely the Keylime framework, to verify (periodically) the software daemons running on the time devices (or their configuration) from a trusted node. Experiments performed on a dedicated test bed set up in the ROOT project with customized time unit devices from SevenSolutions (currently Orolia Spain) allow us to demonstrate that exploiting TPMs and remote attestation in the TDNs is not only helpful but is fundamental for discovering some attacks that would remain otherwise undetected. Our work helps thus TDN operators build more robust, accurate, and secure time synchronization

1. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, more and more infrastructures - including energy grids, transport, industrial automation services, finance, banking applications, and telecommunication networks - need accurate, reliable, and trusted time for their correct operation. Time synchronization has been traditionally required to support billing, alarm functions, or monitoring of delays in Internet Protocol (IP) networks with accuracy of milliseconds or hundreds of microseconds. In present days, time synchronization is highly required in mobile networks, as well as by applications looking for finer time accuracy, less than 10 microseconds or even less than tens of nanoseconds (ns), such as for MIMO (Multiple-Input Multiple Output) transmitter diversity [1]. Moreover, timing information must be delivered via resilient time distribution networks that can operate and respond in case of malfunctions or deliberate security attacks. In the telecommunication sector, the availability of accurate timing information has become a fundamental requirement in the Fifth Generation (5G) mobile networks to provide the expected high Quality of Service (QoS). This requirement poses unprecedented challenges for management of multiple timing sources across the 5G networks. In [2], the authors describe possible 5G time synchronization solutions. Some solutions can be implemented in the RAN (Radio Access Network) domain, while others can run in the transport domain. However, a combination of techniques in both domains could be exploited to create a robust and reliable time distribution solution. Since an increasing range of time-based applications are also considered security critical [3], [4], e.g., in the financial, health, transportation, or energy contexts, the timing information needs appropriate protection against cyber attacks. If such attacks occur, they might seriously affect the applications with potentially devastating effects, like the loss of financial information, data compromise, and even human life loss. This paper describes a solution for mitigating software integrity attacks in a TDN providing time synchronization and distribution in the transport domain. We classify and discuss first the cyber attacks against the installed software (or its configuration) running on the time units operating in an IP-based network. Next, we propose and experiment with a possible solution against software integrity attacks by

exploiting a TPM [5] on the dedicated time units supporting the White Rabbit Precision Time Protocol (WR-PTP) [6], [7] for the distribution of ns-level timing information. TPM 2.0 is a cryptographic chip that enables trust in computing platforms. It is widely used to support the creation of trusted environments on servers, laptops, e.g., TPM 2.0 is required to run Windows 11, and in IOT environments [8]. Before explaining the motivation and contribution of our work, we briefly detail the increased need for accuracy and security in the TDNs. Need for Time Accuracy: The 5G technology offers the benefits of the Time Division Duplex (TDD) [9] spectral efficiency, whose full potential can be exploited if highly accurate time, frequency, and phase synchronization are available at different hierarchical levels of the network architecture. In this sense, 5G networks require increased reliability of the timing sources since a degradation or loss in the timing accuracy and in the precision can impact the RAN performance. On the other hand, legacy networks based on Long-Term Evolution-Frequency Division Duplex (LTE-FDD) can survive lengthy (>1 hour) loss of synchronization without significant performance degradation [10]. The Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS) technologies play a key role in satisfying the stringent requirements for the distribution of an absolute time reference in TDD-based 5G networks: atomic (or sometimes rubidium) clocks may be integrated with GNSS receivers and may be deployed in the TDNs as Centralized Grand Master Clocks (C-GMCs) [1], [11], which generate a Coordinated Universal Time (UTC) traceable time reference. Specifically, the C-GMC obtains a 10MHz clock signal from a rubidium or atomic clock and steers such signal using a One Pulse-per-Second (1-PPS) signal generated by a GNSS receiver. Next, to enable the time distribution to the other nodes in the TDN, the so-called master clocks communicate with multiple slave clocks through appropriate time protocols. For example, the Network Time Protocol (NTP) [12] allows time synchronization over packet-switched networks. Nevertheless, NTP is suitable for large and dynamic networks requiring time accuracy of a few milliseconds. In case of monitoring of delays in IP networks, time synchronization must be accurate within some hundreds of microseconds. In other applications, the accuracy required is much more

stringent, like 5 microseconds for LTE TDD (large cell), 1.5 microseconds for UTRATDD, LTE-TDD (small cell), or even hundreds or tens of nanoseconds for cluster-based synchronization [13]. Among the standardization efforts we mention the ITU-T recommendations G.8271 [13] and G.8272 [14] defining time and phase synchronization aspects in telecommunication networks. In time synchronization distributed via packet based methods, the time synchronization is created by a Primary Reference Time Clock (PRTC) [14] exploiting GNSS technology. The G.8272 standard describes a clock that delivers less than 100 ns phase and time performance suitable for packet networks. To increase performance for phase and time required by the emerging mobile access network technologies and improve security for protection against GNSS outages, the ITU-T organization has consented to a new standard (namely, the enhanced Primary Reference Timing Clock - EPRTC) [15]) that called for better performance, i.e., 30 ns, for time, phase, and frequency.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

The series of works of Alghmadi and Schukat is closest to the work reported in this paper since they have addressed both the network attacks as well as the advanced persistent threats [42], [43] and internal attacks [44] targeting the software or the configuration of the time devices. Nevertheless, the abovementioned research papers have not exploited TC or remote attestation experimentally in a TDN, as presented in this work. For example, [44] discusses how countermeasures based on public key infrastructures, trusted platform modules, network intrusion detection systems and time synchronization supervisors could be adopted to defeat or at least detect such internal attacks but still lacks practical results on employing such technologies in a time synchronization network. The importance of trusted time for various applications is discussed in [19]. The authors examined in a detailed manner the timing capabilities of various TEE (Trusted Execution Environments) that put their root of trust in hardware, including Intel SGX, ARM TrustZone, and TPM. They established that these technologies are susceptible to timing attacks by a malicious operating system and an untrusted network. The same paper ([19]) argued that it is essential to protect time-based primitives across all

layers, i.e., the hardware timers, platform software, and network time packets, even if it did not perform an experimental evaluation in this sense. Some authors of the current paper sketched a preliminary classification of attacks in TDNs and designed a solution for TC-based time distribution in an environment using a Raspberry Pi 4 device (used as an attester node), a trusted Verifier node, and the Keylime software [45]. In parallel, the authors in [46] have analyzed the principal attack vectors in the context of Industry 4.0 applications and highlighted the need for software integrity controls of the TDN nodes. They have also proposed a solution based on TC principles to protect the integrity of the nodes of a time synchronization network. Furthermore, they demonstrated the effectiveness of the proposed approach with a simplified testbed based on low-cost Internet of Things (IoT) devices capable of achieving microsecond-level synchronization accuracy. In the past, the security of the time information in transit over the TDNs has been extensively studied, mainly because unsecured formats were employed for transporting such data [47]. Some works, such as [48], adopted secure data formats, whereas other authors [49] proposed secure timing protocols, like NTP secured through the Network Time Security (NTS) protocol. To secure broadcast time synchronization, [50] set forth using data origin authentication. Regarding remote attestation, several possible implementations exist. Several works performed remote attestation by experimenting with different hardware or software solutions [51], [52], [53]. Some solutions used additional hardware features to perform the attestation, like Intel TXT [54]. A survey of (hardware) remote attestation schemes for various contexts, including cloud computing, IoTs, and critical network infrastructures, can be found in [55]. Others (mainly for embedded systems) removed the hardware components suggesting a solution relying entirely on software [51]. In the IoT networks, the current trend goes toward collective remote attestation (CRA) schemes [56] capable of remotely performing attestation of large networks of (IoT) devices..

3. EXISTING SYSTEM

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4. PROPOSED SYSTEM

This paper describes a solution for mitigating software integrity attacks in a TDN providing time synchronization and distribution in the transport domain. We classify and discuss first the cyber attacks against the installed software (or its configuration) running on the time units operating in an IP-based network. Next, we propose and experiment with a

possible solution against software integrity attacks by exploiting a TPM [5] on the dedicated time units supporting the White Rabbit Precision Time Protocol (WR-PTP) for the distribution of ns-level timing information. TPM 2.0 is a cryptographic chip that enables trust in computing platforms. It is widely used to support the creation of trusted environments on servers, laptops, e.g., TPM 2.0 is required to run Windows 11, and in IoT environments. To protect from software tampering attacks on the dedicated time unit devices, we exploited a TPM, as well as specific Trusted Computing (TC) and remote attestation software. More specifically, we used a software TPM installed on the dedicated time units, along with software implementing the TCG (Trusted Computing Group) software stack specification [35] to interact with the TPM. To measure the software components, like executables, configuration files, and kernel modules, we exploited IMA (Integrity Measurement Architecture) [36], which is part of the Linux kernel since 2009. In addition, we used the Keylime framework to perform TPM-based remote attestation of the time units from a remote trusted node in a highly scalable manner.

SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Fig 1: System Architecture

5. UML DIAGRAMS

1. CLASS DIAGRAM

The cornerstone of event-driven data exploration is the class outline. Both broad practical verification of the application's precision and fine-grained demonstration of the model translation into software code rely on its

Fig 6.3 Upload the Data Sets

In above screen shows upload the all the datasets.

Fig 6.4 View all the datasets

In above screen shows all the available datasets

Fig 6.5 Service Provider Home Page

In above screen shows the Service Provider Home Page

Fig 6.6 View all software Integrity Attacks Detection Results

In above screen shows all software Integrity Attacks Detection Results

Fig 6.7 Software Type results in Bar Chart Graph

In above screen shows the Software Type results in Bar Chart Graph.

7. CONCLUSION

With the rise of 5G networks, mobile telecom operators look for finer time accuracy for synchronization between RAN nodes. At the same time, more and more applications ask for stringent time synchronization in the range of a few micro seconds or even tens of nanoseconds. TDNs may respond to such time requirements by employing specialized time device units and specific timing protocols. Nonetheless, TDNs must also be protected against cyber security attacks since their components and the provided service represent an appealing target for internal and external attackers. We considered a TDN exploiting custom-tailored WR-Z16time unit devices (acting as C-GMCs and D-GMCs) and the WR-PTP protocol for distributing ns-level timing information. We reviewed the attack types applying to TDNs. Then, we focused on the software integrity attacks in which an adversary could compromise the software running on the time unit devices, or its configuration. We designed a TC-enabled solution exploiting the TP Mon the time unit devices, a remote trusted node for monitoring the time devices, and the remote attestation protocol supported by the Key lime framework. With this solution, we successfully detected three types of software integrity attacks involving the (software) daemons or configuration of time devices. Through experiments, we showed the effectiveness of this solution in mitigating all the tested attacks, some of which would have remained undetected otherwise.

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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